

AN NVIVO ANALYSIS OF NATIONAL DRUG POLICY EVALUATION AMONG IMPLEMENTERS

**NOOR AZNIZA ISHAK¹, SITI ROZAINA KAMSANI², MD ZAWAWI ABU BAKAR³,
NUR SYAKIRAN ISMAIL⁴ and ZAINUDIN OMAR⁵**

^{1,2,3,5} School of Applied Psychology, Social Work & Policy, Universiti Utara Malaysia, Kedah, Malaysia.
Email: ¹noorazniza@uum.edu.my, ²rozaina@uum.edu.my, ³zawawi@uum.edu.my, ⁵znudin@uum.edu.my
⁴School of Government, Universiti Utara Malaysia, Kedah, Malaysia. Email: nsai@uum.edu.my

Abstract

Statement by the Vice Chairman of the Malaysian Crime Prevention Foundation (MCPF) stating that the National Drug Policy (DDN) needs to be studied scientifically to measure the overall level of weaknesses in the DDN so that efforts to combat addiction and abuse of illicit substances can be done in an integrated manner given the importance of DDN for the future of the country. In this regard, a study evaluating the effectiveness of the current DDN has been conducted on stakeholders such as AADK Implementers and others as well as academics. The results showed that the majority of implementers agreed that all programs in the DDN that have been implemented by AADK are effective and implemented. Despite showing good performance, there are some things in the DDN that need to be improved. This is to ensure that the DDN and its action plan which emphasizes 'zero drug eradication' can be implemented so that the action plan done previously is strengthened and strengthened to play its role properly.

Keywords: National Drug Policy, Effectiveness Evaluation, Implementer

INTRODUCTION

Drugs are substances produced from plants or synthetic materials, which can cause changes in 'mood', perception and behavior and have psychoactive effects on the addict (Noor Azniza et al, 2017).

As a country that upholds the responsibility to ensure the sustainability and well-being of its people, the government recognizes and is aware of the dangers and effects of the drug problem. Thus, the government has actively exercised its responsibilities, in the context of its territory and through international collaborations, by formulating a drug policy aimed at ensuring the well-being, health, self-esteem and safety of the people as a whole.

This effort has been entrusted to prevention strategies which are now the mainstay of the National Drug Policy (DDN) since 1985. Now in 2019, the DDN which is a policy has been re-drafted to be more comprehensive. The DDN covers all the cores and priority areas that are the pillars in efforts to prevent, treat and rehabilitate as well as enforce drug-related laws more holistically (National Anti-Drug Agency, 2019). The formulation of DDN is seen to be necessary because it is in line with the development and current drug scenario. The formulation of this policy is timely and in line with the government's promise contained in the Book of Hope to deliver more effective services to the people, as contained in Thrust 5 of Promise 52 - combating crime and social ills and encompassing harm reduction measures in tackling drug addiction. As well as enhancing cooperation with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to

reduce relapse rates (National Anti -Drug Agency, 2019).

All drug enforcement agencies and government agencies including non-governmental organizations will make this policy as a reference and guide in efforts to address internal problems in the country. The DDN will assist the government's efforts to achieve the goal of reducing the supply and demand of drugs in Malaysia as well as a reference in addressing the current drug symptom scenario facing the country.

However, this process has become more complicated day by day compared to the era of the 1970s and 1980s as drug dealers are now aggressively influencing the younger generation by using social media and synthetic drugs as attractions. Statistics from the “Drug Information Book 2017” from AADK show a total of 18,444 people involved with new addiction cases and a total of 7,482 for relapse (Drug Information Book, 2017). This is a huge amount in the problem of drug addiction. Saedah (2018) argues that the statistical decline for drug addiction cases seems to be impossible when the problem of drug addiction especially repetitive addiction is still at an alarming level from year to year.

In this regard, to overcome this complexity, the goal of DDN needs to be re -examined as according to the Vice Chairman of the Malaysian Crime Prevention Foundation (MCPF) Lee Lam Thye who stated that DDN needs to be studied scientifically to measure the overall level of weaknesses in DDN so that efforts to combat addiction and the misuse of the banned substance can be done in an integrated manner given the importance of DDN for the future of the country (Bernama, 9 January 2020).

Based on these issues and problems, ongoing research on the implementation strategies of existing policies needs to be done. Therefore, this article will examine the extent of the effectiveness of the policies and programs that have been implemented by AADK.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section will review previous studies related to the effectiveness of a program or indicator that has been conducted by previous researchers. Evaluation of the effectiveness of an indicator is usually related to a policy or policy. According to Dunn (2004) policy evaluation broadly has several methodologies as important analysis to public policy as well as a multi -method approach. According to these scholars policy analysis can be made through problem formulation, projections, monitoring, evaluation and recommendations. For example, data on drug addiction or distribution can be used to assess anti -drug control and evaluate the results, shape the structure of the problem and then re -project policies and provide suggestions for improvement in solving the problem of drug addiction and distribution.

If viewed in terms of drug -related policy strategies, for example enforcement as a policy or strategy described by Akers (2012) who states as a strategy that can control drugs. This policy strategy is not only to restrict and control the supply of drugs but also to curb and curb addiction and reduce the demand for drugs. Therefore, this scholar states that research through public opinion greatly influences public policy, especially drugs, which often require a campaign to stay away from drugs. In addition, enforcement can also be measured by failure and success,

re-addiction or the emergence of offenders or criminals is the best measure in measuring the effectiveness of enforcement.

Mohd Hafiz (2015) has studied the effectiveness of the implementation of drug prevention education courses among KDPM-KDC students. The results of the study found that after the implementation of the PPD course conducted has succeeded in increasing the level of knowledge among students about drugs and drug abuse problems in Malaysia. Despite showing success, the content of PPD courses needs to be improved with a more practical curriculum and hands on in improving the effectiveness of these courses.

Mohd Muzafar Shah et al (2018) studied a meta-analysis of the effectiveness of prevention education programs in the National Anti-Drug Agency. A total of 24 studies were identified that were selected for analysis. The findings of the analysis of the study show that the overall effect of the prevention program is at a moderate level. This shows that the entire prevention program that has been carried out has not reached a high level of effectiveness. The findings of the analysis show that the value for the overall effect of the prevention program evaluated is at a moderate level (0.54) (but the value (0.54) cannot be used because each study must be independent. This indicates that the entire program does not achieve a high level of effectiveness. Successful quantitative types were collected, showing that only four studies used experimental designs, and the rest used survey study design. This indicates a lack of studies examining „effects“ and „causes“, or in other words many studies conducted only studies on „what?“ and „why?“, but less studies that study on „how?“. While studies that study on „effects“ and „causes“ are important to see the effectiveness of drug prevention that has been conducted in Malaysia either in the form of educational programs or the development of prevention modules. With any such study will form an instrument, module and index formation that can help the AADK.

Rozmi et al (2019) have evaluated the Effectiveness of SHIELDS Program Using Pre and Post Program Approaches. The findings of this study show that the SHIELDS program has succeeded in achieving the target of providing knowledge to the students involved. However, if we look at the difference scores before and after and the follow-up 3 months after that found that the SHIELDS program only moderately contributed to the increase in knowledge of its participants in aspects of knowledge about drugs, including the physical effects of drug use, actions to be taken by adolescents if there are friends they are involved with drug abuse, the means of distribution and sale of drugs, the dangers of drugs and risky drug-related activities. Changes in participants' attitudes before and after showed not much change in the mean score of SHIELDS participants' attitudes towards self, future and life goals, family as well as attitudes towards personality and morals. Tracing study was also conducted to examine the trend of change of participants throughout their lives to measure the effectiveness of SHIELDS or other drug prevention programs, in addition to creating profile data of former SHIELDS participants. Azizul Halim Yahya et al (2019) have studied the Effectiveness of AADK Public Awareness Program Through Social Marketing Approach. Referring to the campaign messages conducted, the results of the study in the three states showed that the actual message conveyed has not reached the level to make the recipients aware of the message. Various factors are raised such

as the content of the message used, the choice of delivery medium and the target group. So far, the coherence in the delivery of the anti -drug campaign message is still loose as it focuses more on the general message and the ill effects of drugs. The results of the study in the three states found that community involvement in jointly combating these symptoms is very low. The frequency of organizing and implementing anti-drug campaigns should be increased and the location of the campaign should be mobilized comprehensively covering offices, schools and institutions of higher learning as well as areas of public focus such as shopping malls and entertainment centers. This scholar therefore suggested that the establishment of a campaign mechanism for all states should be done. This is because each state has a different way of campaigning. With only one guideline the distinction between states can be made.

Siti Norlina et al (2015) conducted a study to identify residents' perceptions of religious programs and evaluate the effectiveness of religious programs in helping the success of the treatment and rehabilitation of residents and study the relevance of the implementation of religious modules in rehabilitation institutions to be applied to other rehabilitation institutions. Conducted at the Cure and Care Rehabilitation Center (CCRC) in Bachok, Besut District AADK, Kemaman District AADK and Kuala Terengganu CCSC. A total of 74 respondents were selected from Muslim female trainees and underwent religious modules at the CCRC as well as interviews with 13 respondents consisting of OKP and 9 staff of CCRC, District AADK and CCSC who were directly involved with the module. The findings of the study showed that the trainees, OKPs and staff at CCRC Bachok agreed that religious programs are very important to ensure the involvement and effectiveness of rehabilitation using a religious approach.

Amin Al Haadi et al (2018) have studied the Construction of AADK Career Therapy Model among AADK Trainees. Overall, the study of the construction of the AADK Career Therapy Model has had a positive impact on the experimental respondents and is expected to help in completing the rehabilitation process implemented in Drug rehabilitation centers in Malaysia. The results of the career therapy model study showed that there was a significant improvement in the self -concept of the study respondents. This improvement will help respondents in understanding themselves, others, self -strengths, self -weaknesses and also build a more positive self -concept. Respondents' self -control locus activities were implemented under the theme of coping mechanisms that focused on relapse management activities. The results of the self -control locus test, the post -experimental group results showed a slight increase for the self -control locus when compared to the control group. The effect of the career therapy model on the level of willingness to change of the respondents showed an increase in the level of readiness to change but was not significant. Demographic factors have influenced the effectiveness of trainee career planning based on the analysis of regression data performed. There are seven demographic factors that have been identified to affect career maturity, namely: education level, marital status, age of drug use, frequency of relapses, duration of addiction and frequency of admission to rehabilitation centers and prisons.

Amin Al Haadi et al (2018) conducted a Meta-Analysis Study of the Effectiveness of Treatment and Rehabilitation Program in the National Anti-Drug Agency (AADK) involving eight quantitative studies and fourteen qualitative studies that are in the custody of AADK and also

those in several Institutions Higher Education in Malaysia. In general, the results of past studies indicate that most treatments show positive results. There are various forms of studies and approaches that have been studied in drug rehabilitation centers in the country and there are also some that have been found to be effective by researchers. However, there is no specific focus that can really help the AADK in strengthening its treatment and rehabilitation services.

Haslee et al (2016) conducted a study on the effectiveness of anti -drug (PDH) programs in 2016. The objective of this study was to evaluate the effectiveness of PDH programs through six main programs determined based on seven evaluation indicators (1) Number of new addicts, 2) The number of addiction dens successfully cleaned, 3) The impact of the all-out drug fight program quantitatively and qualitatively, 4) Stakeholder commitment to all programs conducted in the program, 5) Community inclusion of all-out drug program activities, 7) Public readiness for anti-drug programs). The study was quantitative in nature involving numbers and figures, however, qualitative data were also collected through semi -structured interviews and analyzed to support and reinforce the quantitative findings. The data collection method for this study is in the form of stratified sampling technique. The results show that the decrease in the rate of new addicts detected in the focus area if generalized to the national rate of new addicts is much lower or a reduction of 55.0%. Clearance of 71.4% of the total number of addiction nests registered and profiled in the focus areas within eight months. The overall impact of the program was 80.4% on the community based on measures of the variables of accessibility, visibility, readiness, awareness, knowledge and skills among community leaders and members. Detection and detention programs (preventive, nesting and integrated operations) had the highest impact on the community, followed by omnipresence programs, media and anti -drug icons. The commitment shown by stakeholders to the PDH Campaign is very high. Community inclusion occurs in 85.7% of PDH's focus areas, involving the roles of all parties, namely non -governmental organizations (NGOs), the private sector, private individuals and community leaders. The results obtained also showed that community leaders played the most important role with an involvement rate of 78.6%, followed by NGOs (57.1%), the private sector (35.7%) and private individuals (35.7%). Overall, the findings of this study indicate that the all-out anti-drug campaign is very successful and effective in reducing the problem of drug addiction.

Haslee et al (2016) who conducted the Evaluation Study of the Effectiveness of the Anti-Drug Program (PDH) showed that the anti-drug campaign is very successful and effective in overcoming the problem of drug addiction. Decrease in the rate of new addicts detected in the focus areas of the PDH Campaign. The findings of the study showed that within eight months of the PDH Campaign, a total of 2,459 addicts were arrested and tested positive for drugs. Of these, only 518 people or 21.1% were new addicts. If generalized to the national new addict rate, the findings of this study are much lower or a reduction of 55.0%. Before the campaign was launched, the new addict rate recorded in 2015 was 76.1%. Clearance of 71.4% of the total number of addiction nests registered and profiled in the focus areas within eight months. There are no records showing these nests were reactivated after cleaning.

METHODOLOGY

The method of this study is qualitative using an interview approach conducted on a sample of experts in the academic field and stakeholders from AADK, PDRM, Prisons and KKM. The instrument of this study is based on information from the book National Drug Policy (2019), Controlled Drug Program Strategy 2021-2025, Strategic Plan 2015-2020 and International Anti-Drug Prevention Best Practices modified according to the suitability of the study. The analysis of this interview data used Nvivo 12 software program which aims to obtain an overview of the study categories to answer the objectives formed.

RESULT

Enforcement

Based on the interviews conducted showed that most of the Informants stated that the enforcement carried out by AADK was effective. The effectiveness according to the Informant from the aspect of increasing the arrest of hardcore and new drug addicts as well as people who process drugs in High Risk Areas (KBT) compared to the previous year. Apart from that, according to the Informant, the effectiveness is also seen from the aspect of the amount of allocation provided by the government and also sufficient AADK staff. The improvement of the new online system has also made it easier for the community to lodge complaints and many complaints have been received since the system was used. Similarly, the aspect of collaboration between the AADK and other agencies such as PDRM, Customs, JPJ, UPP and other enforcement agencies has succeeded in increasing the arrests of drug addicts.

However, there are some informants who stated that enforcement is less effective due to several factors, namely;

1. Logistics

The lack of vehicles and logistics equipment is a constraint to the enforcement carried out by the AADK.

2. Drugs are readily available

The ineffectiveness of enforcement is seen in the increase in the number of new drugs and the wide variety of drugs that are readily available.

3. Training and skills

Training and skills in the aspects of espionage and arrest need to be enhanced as done by the PDRM narcotics division.

4. Programs in recovery

Enforcement of programs in rehabilitation is poorly monitored as is done by the Malaysian Prisons Department under the Parole Program.

5. Staff integrity

Corruption in a handful of staff is a factor in the growing issue of addiction and few arrests have been made.

6. Technology

Today's technological changes are the reason why enforcement is less effective. This is because that technology equipment does not keep up with current changes, lack of exposure and training on the use of technology today.

7. Cooperation with other agencies.

The involvement and cooperation of academics needs to be enhanced to strengthen the effectiveness in tackling this drug problem. Collaboration also needs to be enhanced with other enforcement agencies.

International Cooperation

The majority of the Informants agreed that AADK plays a good role or cooperation internationally. AADK actively collaborates with agencies abroad from the Region and International in conducting discussions, meetings, activities and MOU agreements to find mechanisms to curb the drug problem.

Some informants felt that the AADK needed to increase their involvement at the international level. For example discussions on border issues involving regional countries need to be stepped up. The program to send AADK staff abroad needs to be held more frequently. The same goes for information sharing programs at the international level.

Prevention Education

According to the Informant, various programs and activities related to the aspect of Prevention Education have been implemented by AADK at the community level.

However, there were also informants who stated the need for Prevention Education by the AADK to be intensified. Informants also gave the view that this situation may be due to the culture of the community that does not care about the situation around them. Some of the informants are of the view that the community still thinks that the task of Prevention Education should be borne entirely by AADK.

Informants who were interviewed said that Prevention Education activities were implemented in schools by AADK. These activities are carried out by AADK together with other agencies such as PDRM in conveying information related to drugs.

Some informants also stated that prevention education at the school level was less effective due to the lack of programs implemented.

In the aspect of disseminating drug -related information through traditional media, most of the Informants stated that it was less effective because the dissemination of information did not focus on the target group, especially among parents and youths themselves. Meanwhile, some

informants are of the view that there is a need to modify the drug -related information method made by AADK to increase the effectiveness of the campaign. Other informants were of the view that environmental conditions such as rural areas made it difficult for the AADK to disseminate information and provide awareness education to the community more effectively.

According to the Informant prevention education using new media shows high effectiveness. AADK has used various social media mediums such as Facebook, Youtube, Instagram and others to disseminate information and educate the community. Through this social media, a clear explanation is given to the target group about the consequences that befall if they are involved with drugs. However, some informants think that Prevention Education through new media is less effective. According to them, the delivery strategy through this new media is less creative and not diverse.

Treatment and Rehabilitation Program

In general, the treatment and rehabilitation program implemented by the AADK has greatly helped the trainees in self -change such as returning to the original nature as well as improving the skills and identity of a trainee. There were also informants who stated that treatment and rehabilitation programs were less effective. Among them is due to some parts of the module such as self -rehabilitation need to be improved according to the current situation. Similarly, from the aspect of recovery time needs to be reviewed because the current time period is very short.

DISCUSSION

DDN involving Enforcement shows that the executor is satisfied with the implementation of the task of implementing, planning and enforcement by AADK on drug -related offenses. Similarly, the domain of Education where the majority of implementers agree and are satisfied with the cooperation between the community and schools in terms of delivery and dissemination of information related to drugs as well as prevention programs and activities carried out. Similarly, the aspect of disseminating information related to drugs through traditional and new media where all respondents are satisfied with the dissemination of information and prevention. In terms of the social inclusion program, it also shows that the program has received good cooperation from the community and has succeeded in building the self -confidence of trainees to face challenges when they leave later as well as help create job opportunities. In the domain of International Cooperation also shows the implementers agree that AADK plays a good role or cooperation at the international level. The AADK also actively collaborates with agencies abroad from the region and internationally in conducting discussions, meetings, activities and MOU memorandums to find mechanisms to curb the drug problem. Similarly, the Treatment and Rehabilitation domain is also satisfied and stated that the treatment and rehabilitation programs implemented by the AADK such as detoxification treatment, methadone, psychosocial and spiritual rehabilitation are effective. This is because these programs have helped the trainees a lot in self-change such as returning to the original nature as well as improving the skills and identity of a trainee. Similarly, the aspects of justice and punishment implemented in Malaysia in accordance with procedures and implemented

effectively to curb the drug problem. In terms of providing infrastructure to the trainees also showed that all respondents agreed that the trainees were provided with various facilities such as shelter, food and drink during rehabilitation.

While the domain of Harm Reduction also shows that the implementers agree that the AADK has performed their duties effectively together with other enforcement agencies as well as the MOH in reducing harm resulting from drug abuse. Respondents argued that these agencies have successfully enhanced rehabilitative treatment programs such as detoxification, methadone as well as psychosocial as well as psychospiritual rehabilitation in reducing drug harm to trainees. Similarly, in terms of improving HIV treatment prevention and detection activities through the implementation of the Needle & Syringe Exchange Program (NSEP) and infectious diseases implemented among trainees, the majority of respondents agreed that this activity is constantly monitored by the AADK and has been greatly enhanced to reduce harm. Drug abuse. In terms of raising awareness and understanding of infectious diseases and the consequences of drug abuse, the AADK and other enforcement agencies have always given a high commitment together in providing information to the community through prevention education with various activities have been done to raise awareness about the harms of taking drugs. Therefore, based on the discussion, it can be concluded that the majority of implementers agree that all programs in the DDN that have been implemented by AADK are effective and implemented.

CONCLUSION

The AADK has implemented many programs or activities in the field of prevention, treatment and rehabilitation, enforcement, including program participation at the international level. The overall findings show that the programs conducted by AADK are encouraging. This means that the programs implemented by AADK are good. Therefore, AADK only needs to continue the existing program because it has been accepted by all parties. Despite showing good performance but there are domains that need to be improved such as;

- 1) Programs related to international cooperation need to be further enhanced to improve external drug control.
- 2) Organize programs to increase community confidence in supporting the prevention of drug trafficking.
- 3) The program conducted should be in line with the existing agencies to enforce drug abuse.
- 4) There is a need to develop an AADK training center for the purpose of enhancing the competencies and enforcement skills of AADK officers on par with PDRM such as the Special Action Unit.
- 5) Spiritual programs are also important to be implemented comprehensively as implemented in the Northern Zone. The spiritual modules implemented in the Northern Zone are seen as special when each activity is implemented with a comprehensive spiritual approach

starting from the practice of prayer, sunnah prayers, recitation and memorization of 14 surahs.

- 6) Prevention education can also be done through approaches such as campaigns and infographic information. SMS alerts can be created as a platform for young people to get information directly to them. SMS alerts as new media can be channeled via WhatsApp, Telegram, Instagram, Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and other new media.
- 7) Furthermore, drug prevention education through the mosque pulpit also has an impact on the congregation present at the time of the sermon delivered.
- 8) In implementing laws and policies, clear responsibilities between agencies need to be performed. For example, for enforcement under the responsibility of the police and AADK, the role is to implement rehabilitation, prevention and rehabilitation interventions. This division of responsibilities will further increase effectiveness in dealing with drug issues. Even so, there must be integrated cooperation between all agencies involved, especially PDRM and AADK.
- 9) For trainees who have successfully left the world of drugs completely, should be brought as a 'Role Model' to other former trainees to be mentors to them. This can be done through the establishment of a Mentoring program as a support system for them. In addition, the program can recognize the Role Model through special payments/ consolation as a motivation to support the program. This program needs to be done continuously for the continuity of a comprehensive support system.
- 10) Surveys in several KBT zones show that spiritual programs such as the Tazkiyah Program and the Isra Program which are implemented comprehensively to People Subject to Supervision (OKP) and trainees were found to show a positive effect for those zones. Therefore such programs are proposed and expanded in other zones.
- 11) Improvements to policies and acts related to coordination of duties between agencies also need to be considered/reviewed. For example, coordinating the same drug act for each implementing agency for customs, immigration, marine, UPP, PDRM and AADK. This means, the Drugs Act contained detailed tasks to each executor for different agencies.
- 12) For Education programs in the community, PIBG meetings can be used as a platform for exposure and awareness to parents. The police and AADK can be invited to provide information or campaigns on drugs to students' next of kin.
- 13) The majority of the zones in the study area have used a spiritual approach in part or in whole in rehabilitation and treatment programs within and outside the institution. Therefore, the spirituality approach is a pillar of the strength of drug treatment and rehabilitation programs in Malaysia.

Acknowledgement

We thank to all respondents who were involved in this study, our research assistant, and the most important regards to Agensi Anti Dadah Kebangsaan Malaysia for this grant.

Reference

1. Agensi Antidadah Kebangsaan (2020). *Laporan Dadah 2020*: Putrajaya: Kementerian Dalam Negeri.
2. Agensi Anti Dadah Kebangsaan (AADK) (2019). *Dasar Dadah Negara*: Putrajaya: Kementerian Dalam Negeri.
3. Agensi Anti Dadah Kebangsaan (AADK) (2018). *Buku Maklumat Dadah*: Putrajaya: Kementerian Dalam Negeri.
4. Ashley, C. (2019). The differences between indexes and scales. Atas talian <https://www.thoughtco.com/indexes-and-scales-3026544>
5. Bernama (9 Januari 2020). Dasar dadah negara perlu dikaji semula – MCPF. Atas talian <https://www.bernama.com/bm/news.php?id=1805407>
6. Cates, W.M. (1985). *Practical guides for educational research*. Kuala Lumpur: Institute of Language and Literature (DBP).
7. Drug Policy Metrics Map (2020). The Drug Policy Metrics Map is an online tool developed for the cross comparison of international policies related to illegal drugs. Atas talian <https://drugmap.cdpe.org/about.html>
8. Haslee Sharil et al (2016). Kajian Penilaian Keberkesanan Program Perangi Dadah Habis habisan (PDH). Persatuan Kaunseling Malaysia (Perkama International)
9. International Drug Policy Consortium (2017). A global network promoting objective and open debate on drug policy. Atas talian <https://idpc.net/>
10. Noor Azniza Ishak, Mahmood Nazar Mohamed, Jamaludin Mustaffa, Kamal Ab Hamid, Azemi Shaari & Mohd Hilmi Hamzah (2017). *Kajian penyalahgunaan daun ketum dalam kalangan pelajar sekolah menengah di negeri Kedah dan Perlis*. Laporan Kajian. Sintok: Universiti Utara Malaysia.
11. Saedah A. Ghani (2018). Family functioning and its relation with self-esteem among drug addicts. *Malaysian Anti-Drugs Journal*, 3&4, 91-106.